

**СБОРНИК ДОКЛАДИ ОТ
НАУЧНА КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ
„ЗНАНИЕ, НАУКА, ИНОВАЦИИ,
ТЕХНОЛОГИИ“**

Proceedings of
Knowledge, Science, Innovation, Technology Conference

3/2023

ISSN 2815-3480

**Knowledge,
Science and
Innovations
Institute**

Издаелство „Институт за знание, наука и иновации“

ANCIENT REFERENCES ON THE SCIPIOS THRACIAN CAMPAIGN IN 190 BC

Jordan Iliev, PhD

Research Centre for History and Archaeology of War

***Abstract:** In 190 BC for the very first time Roman troops passed through Thrace; this happened within a campaign from Greece to Asia Minor, which was part of the Syrian war (192 – 188 BC). In this paper the available ancient sources on this issue are collected and analyzed. The data on the movement of the army and the conducted battles are considered. A special attention is paid to the role of Philip V of Macedon, who accompanied the Romans; his diligent support is explained with an information of Cassius Dio: Antiochus annexed some places in Thrace, that belonged to him. The information about military clashes between the passing troops and the local Thracians is also discussed.*

***Key words:** Ancient Thrace, Rome, Philip V of Macedon, military campaigns.*

Introduction

In 196 BC Antiochus III the Great (223 – 187 BC) start campaigning in Thrace at the head of significant land and naval forces; he had quickly established his control over the Thracian Chersonese and used it as a base for several raids in the surrounding Thracian lands in the following years (GRAINGER 2015: 151-186). The Romans carefully watched his operations, even more because of Hannibal's presence in the Syrian royal court. There was even a rumor that the Carthaginian general prepared a plan for war against Rome through an attack from Thrace (HAMMOND & WALBANK 2001: 450; GRAINGER 2002: 112). Not long after that there was a direct military clash between Rome and Antiochus III, commonly referred to as the Syrian war (192 – 188 BC) (WALBANK 2014: 186-222; GRAINGER 2002: Pass.; GRAINGER 2015: 151-186; ERDKAMP 2017: 1-9; DMITRIEV 2018: 1-6). In the course of this war Roman troops passed for the very first time through the Thracian lands on their way from Greece to Asia Minor. This first Roman passage has not received enough attention in the studies on the history of Ancient Thrace (ТАЧЕВА 1997: 54; ЦБЕТКОВА 2008: 232; ПЕТКОВ 2011: 44; ДЕЛЕВ 2017: 41). The following lines tries to fill this significant gap (they are based on a previous paper, already published in Bulgarian, see ИЛИЕВ 2022: 282-289).

A remark on the diligent assistance of Philip V

Antiochus III landed with confidence in Greece, but still the ancient writers pointed out several organizational and tactical errors in the overall conduct of his military campaign. He lost catastrophically at the Battle of

Thermopylae in 191 BC and quickly retired to Asia Minor. The Romans decided to transfer the war in Asia to deal with the Syrian threat. However, they preferred to pass by land through Macedonia and Thrace, for which many relied on the assistance of Philip V of Macedon (221 – 179 BC); after the defeat in the Second Macedonian War (200 – 197 BC), he was counted among the Roman allies and there were a number of occasions to aid them, including with military forces (WALBANK 2014: 189).

In ancient literature various explanations are given of the remarkable diligence with which the Macedonian king assisted the Romans during the Syrian War. As it seems, more prevalent is the emotional explanation presented by Appian, according to which the Macedonian king had not decided on which side to join in the clash between Rome and Syria, until Antiochus III took care of the burial of the fallen Philippian soldiers at the Battle of Cynoscephalae (197 BC) (HAMMOND & WALBANK 2001: 451; WALBANK 2014: 200); this act was interpreted as directed personally against him and therefore he choose to support the Romans (App., Syr., 3.16).

There must undoubtedly have been other more practical reasons, as an information of Cassius Dio seems very convincing; according to this author, Philip V assiduously supported the Romans:

„διά τε ἄλλα καὶ ὅτι ὁ Ἀντίοχος χωρία αὐτοῦ ἐν τῇ Θράκῃ τινὰ ἐπεσπάσατο / above all, because Antiochus annexed some places in Thrace that belonged to him“ (Cass. Dio, 19.1 = Zon. 9.19).

It is not known where the places (χωρία) in question were situated. Perhaps Philip V aspired to the cities along the Thracian Aegean coast. He himself later (during diplomatic talks about the fate of these cities) revealed to Roman envoys that once he had an advantageous offer from Antiochus III to fight on his side: he was promised a large sum of money and all cities in Greece (Liv. 39.28.6-9). However, he preferred to remain loyal to Rome.

The passing through Macedonia and Thrace

The idea of passing through Macedonia and Thrace, a hitherto unprecedented route, was attributed to Lucius Cornelius Scipio, consul in 190 BC, or to his famous brother Publius Cornelius Scipio Africanus, who accompanied him as a military advisor (RICH 2015: 92). The expedition was preceded by a six-month truce in Greece (HAMMOND & WALBANK 2001: 453).

The march itself was preceded by a special reconnaissance mission to the Macedonian king, conducted by Tiberius Sempronius Gracchus, handed down by Livy:

„[...] et consul ab Amphissa Thessaliam repetit, ut per Macedoniam Thraeciamque duceret in Asiam. Tum Africanus fratri: 'iter, quod insistis, L. Scipio, ego quoque approbo; sed totum id vertitur in voluntate Philippi, qui si imperio nostro fidus est, et iter et commeatus et omnia, quae in longo itinere exercitus alunt iuvantque, nobis suppeditabit; si is destituit, nihil per Thraeciam satis tutum habebis; itaque prius regis animum explorari placet. Optime explorabitur, si nihil ex praeparato agentem opprimet qui inittetur.' Ti. Sempronius Gracchus, longe tum acerrimus iuvenum, ad id delectus per dispositos equos prope incredibili celeritate ab Amphissa – inde enim est dimissus – die tertio Pellam pervenit. In convivio rex erat et in multum vini processerat; ea ipsa remissio animi suspicionem dempsit novare eum quicquam velle. Et tum quidem comiter acceptus hospes, postero die commeatus exercitui paratos benigne, pontes in fluminibus factos, vias, ubi transitus difficiles erant, munitas vidit. haec referens eadem, qua ierat, celeritate Thaumacis occurrit consuli. Inde certiore et maiore spe laetus exercitus ad praeparata omnia in Macedoniam pervenit. Venientis regio apparatu et accepit et prosecutus est rex. Multa in eo et dexteritas et humanitas visa, quae commendabilia apud Africanum erant, virum sicut ad cetera egregium, ita a comitate, quae sine luxuria esset, non aversum. Inde non per Macedoniam modo sed etiam Thraeciam prosequente et praeparante omnia Philippo ad Hellespontum perventum est / [After receiving the command of the army] the consul returned from Amphissa to Thessaly, with the intention of leading his troops through Macedonia and Thrace. Here Africanus told to his brother, Lucius Scipio: «So and I, Lucius Scipio, I approve the path you choose. But the whole enterprise depends on the predisposition of Philip. If he remains loyal to us, he will provide us with a passage, provisions, and all things, necessary to support an army in a long march. But if he does not remain [loyal], you will not find safety in any part of Thrace. Therefore, in my opinion, first we need to understand the disposition of the king. He will be best tested if the person being sent arrives suddenly at him, without doing anything according to a previously agreed plan». Tiberius Sempronius Gracchus, a young man, most active of all the youths at that time, was selected to perform this task. By means of relays of horses and moving at extraordinary speed, he left Amphissa, from where he was sent, and reached Pella on the third day. The king feasted and was advanced with the cups: this relaxation of the mind removed any suspicion of possible intention to deceive with his behavior. The guest was kindly received and the next day he saw supplies in abundance, already prepared for the army, bridges over rivers and roads, made where there were difficulties of transport. Returning from this reconnaissance mission at the same speed, with whom he

arrived, he met the consul in Thaumacus. From all this learned, the army rejoiced, with safer and higher hopes go for Macedonia, where everything that was needed was prepared. On their arrival, the king received them with regal splendor, and accompanied them during the march. He showed a lot of desire and good mood, which pleased Africanus, who although incomparable in other respects, was not indifferent to good manners, as long as they weren't excessive. Philip accompanied them not only as they passed through Macedonia, but also through Thrace, taking care of everything necessary, and thus they reached the Hellespont“ (Liv. 37.7.8-16).

Thus, in 190 BC for the first time Roman troops crossed through Thrace, led by the two Scipios. The presented story lacks some important details. The number of troops passing is not known for sure, but it was definitely a matter of significant forces, inasmuch as the Scipio brothers had an army numbering about 50,000 soldiers on the eve of the Battle of Magnesia (probably in December 190 BC, see GRAINGER 2002: 361).

The good awareness of the situation in Thrace, demonstrated by Publius Cornelius Scipio Africanus, is noteworthy. The strong positions of Philip V in the Thracian lands, known from previous events (ИЛИЕВ 2023: Pass.), are also visible. It is especially indicative, for instance, that disorganized soldiers of Antiochus III were escorted by Macedonian units from Naupactus through Thrace to Lysimachia (Liv. 36.33.6).

The mission of Tiberius Sempronius Gracchus is missing in Appian (see RICH 2015: 93). The information about the passage through Thrace, provided by this author, is much more limited:

„Πόπλιος δὲ Σκιπίων ἀφικόμενος ἐς Αἰτωλίαν μετὰ τοῦ ὑπάτου, καὶ Μανίου στρατὸν παραλαβὼν, τὰς μὲν ἐν Αἰτωλία πολιορκίας ὑπερεῖδεν ὡς μικρὸν ἔργον, καὶ τοῖς Αἰτωλοῖς δεομένοις ἐπέτρεψεν αὐτοῖς ἐς Ῥώμην πρεσβεῦσαι περὶ σφῶν, ἐπὶ δὲ τὸν Ἀντίοχον ἠπεύγετο πρὶν ἐκβῆναι τῷ ἀδελφῷ τὴν στρατηγίαν. διὰ δὲ Μακεδόνων ὄδευε καὶ Θρακῶν ἐπὶ τὸν Ἑλλήσποντον, δυσχερῆ καὶ χαλεπὴν ὁδὸν αὐτῷ γενομένην ἄν, εἰ μὴ Φίλιππος ὁ Μακεδὼν ὁδοποιεῖ καὶ ὑπεδέχετο καὶ παρέπεμπεν ἐξευγμένοις τε ποταμοῖς ἐκ πολλοῦ καὶ ἀγοραῖς ἐτοίμοις / Meanwhile, Publius Scipio arrived in Aetolia and received the command of the army from Manius. He immediately renounced the siege of the Aetolian cities as a minor job and allowed their inhabitants to send a new envoy to Rome, while he himself hastened to face Antiochus, before his brother's command to expired. He moved by land through Macedonia and Thrace to the Hellespont; that would be a very difficult transition for him, if Philip of Macedon did not repair the roads, entertained him, escorted him, made bridges across the streams some time before and provided him with provisions“ (App., Syr., 5.23).

It is not possible to trace in the fullest detail where exactly the Romans passed through Thrace, but their direction of movement from west to east to the Thracian Chersonese reminds of the route of the future Roman road Via Egnatia. A later speech by Philip V is preserved, in which he himself listed the services, which he made for the Romans:

„[...] *et insequenti consuli L. Scipioni, cum terra statuisset ducere exercitum ad Hellespontum, non iter tantum per regnum nostrum dedi, sed vias etiam munivi, pontes feci, commeatus praebui; nec per Macedoniam tantum, sed per Thraciam etiam, ubi inter cetera pax quoque praestanda a barbaris erat / and to the next consul, Lucius Scipio, when he decided to lead his army to the Hellespont by land, I didn't just give him the right of passage through my kingdom, but I also made roads, built bridges, provided provisions; I did this not only through Macedonia, but also through Thrace, where, among other things, I had to keep peace with the barbarians*“ (Liv. 39.28.8-9).

New information in this speech is the explicitly stated necessity for the Macedonian king to maintain „peace with the barbarians“, which should be interpreted as meaning, that his authority in the Thracian lands was not unlimited.

The Roman Navy in support of the land forces

In parallel with the movement of the ground forces, most of the Roman fleet, available at that time in the Eastern Mediterranean, went to the Hellespont by sea:

„*Αἰούιος δ' ὁ ναύαρχος ἐπεὶ τῆς ὁδοιπορίας τῶν Σκιπιώνων ἐπόθετο, Πανσίμαχον μὲν τὸν Ῥόδιον μετὰ τῶν Ῥοδίων νεῶν ἐν τῇ Αἰολίδι κατέλιπε, καὶ μέρος τι τοῦ ἰδίου στόλου, ταῖς δὲ πλείοσιν ἐς τὸν Ἑλλήσποντον ἔπλει τὸν στρατὸν ὑποδεξόμενος. καὶ Σηστός μὲν αὐτῷ καὶ Ῥοίτειον καὶ ὁ Ἀχαιῶν λιμὴν καὶ τινα ἄλλα προσέθετο, Ἀβυδὸν δὲ ἀπειθοῦσαν ἐπολιόρκει / Livius, the commander of the fleet, when he learned, that the Scipios were on the march, left Pausimachus, the Rhodian, with the Rhodian ships and a part of his own, in Aeolis, and he himself sailed with the greater part to the Hellespont to meet the army. Sestos, Rhaeteum the Achaean Harbour and some other places surrendered. Abydos refused [to surrender] and was besieged*“ (App., Syr., 5.23).

Nothing is known about the Seleucid reaction to the Roman naval operations. It is only reported that at the same time Seleucus, the son of Antiochus III, was ravaging the lands of Eumenes, king of Pergamon, and besieged Pergamos (App., Syr., 5.26).

A collision with the Thracians

In historiography it is assumed that the Roman army passed smoothly through Thrace (after ДЕЛИБ 2017: 41 – „The Roman army crossed unimpeded

through Southern Thrace and passed into Asia“). This is not quite the case. In the later story of the ambush, into which Vulso fell, Livy added several sentences about a past incident that happened on the way of the Scipios through the Thracian lands. The source of the information was the Roman analyst Quintus Claudius Quadrigarius:

„[...] *quamquam tunc quoque Claudius auctor est ad quindecim milia Thraecum praecedenti ad exploranda loca agmen Muttini Numidae occurrisse. Quadringentos equites fuisse Numidas, paucos elephantos; Muttinis filium per medios hostes cum centum quinquaginta delectis equitibus perrupisse; eundem mox, cum iam Muttines in medio elephantis locatis, in cornua equitibus dispositis manum cum hoste conseruisset, terrorem ab tergo praebuisse, atque inde turbatos equestri velut procella hostis ad peditum agmen non accessisse / about 15 thousand Thracians stood in the way of the Numidian Mutin, who was sent forward, to explore the area, as he had 400 Numidian horsemen and several elephants. Mutin's son then made his way through the enemies with the 150 cavalry he commanded, and immediately, after Mutin with the elephants located in the center [of the line] and with the horsemen distributed on the wings, he fought with his enemies, attacked the Thracians to their horror from the back. As a result of this cavalry attack, the enemies were so disorganized, that they dared not then approach the Roman infantry column... [In this case] the Thracians proved to be more peaceful for no other reason, but because then [the army] carried with them less prey than they wished” (Cl. Quadrig., Ann., 7, fr. 65 = Liv. 38.41.12-14).*

If these data are to be believed, in this incident the number of Thracians was 50% higher than those who attacked Vulso two years later. Unfortunately, nothing is noted in this case about their tribal affiliation and the location of the collision; having in mind the disposition of the narrative in Livy's work it is permissible to think that the participants and the geographical position of the two events were relatively close (ΠΕΤΚΟΒ 2011: 44).

Identity between the Thracians of 190 and 188 BC can be suggested on the basis of the following text of Appian:

„[...] *περὶντάς τε ἐπὶ Ἀντίοχον ἐς τὴν Ἀσίαν διὰ Θράκης καὶ Μακεδονίας ὁδὸν οὐκ εὐμαρῆ παρέπεμπεν οἰκείοις τέλεσι καὶ τροφαῖς, ὁδοποῶν καὶ ποταμοῦς δυσπόρους ζευγνὺς καὶ τοὺς ἐπικειμένους Θρᾶκας διακόπτων, ἕως ἐπὶ τὸν Ἑλλήσποντον ἤγαγεν [...] οἱ δὲ Θρᾶκες οἶδε Ῥωμαίους ἀπὸ τῆς ἐπ’ Ἀντιόχῳ νίκης, ἐπανιόντας, οὐκέτι Φιλίππου παρόντος, τὴν τε λείαν ἀφείλοντο καὶ πολλοὺς διέφθειραν, ᾧ καὶ μάλιστα ἐπεδείχθη ὅσον αὐτοὺς ἀνιόντας ὅσον ὤνησεν ὁ Φίλιππος / [...] when [the Romans] were moving against Antiochus in Asia, passing through Thrace and Macedonia on a difficult road, he [Philip V]*

escorted them with his own troops, provide them with food and money, repair the roads, make bridges on impassable streams and scattered the hostile Thracians, until he gets them to the Hellespont [...] But the Thracians attacked the Romans on their return after the victory over Antiochus, when Philip was no more with them, they took away their prey and many were killed. So it became clear how much service Philip had given them on the way out“ (App., Mac., 5).

This testimony is counted among the rare documented during the Hellenistic era examples of interaction of different Thracian tribes (ТАЧЕБА 1997: 55).

Establishment of Roman control over the Thracian Chersonese

In historiography is maintained the statement, that „[...] the advancing Roman army conquered Lysimachia and the entire peninsula without resistance [...]“ (ЦБЕТКОБА 2008: 232-233). Ancient sources, however, refute such an observation.

Livy briefly told the last stages of the transition through Thrace:

„per idem fere tempus consuli, transgresso Aeniorum Maronitarumque finis, nuntiatur victam regiam classem ad Myonnesum relictamque a praesidio Lysimachiam esse. Id multo quam de navali victoria laetius fuit, utique postquam eo venerunt, refertaque urbs omnium rerum com meatibus velut in adventum exercitus praeparatis eos exceptit, ubi inopiam ultimam laboreque in obsidenda urbe proposuerant sibi. paucos dies stativa habuere, impedimenta aegrique ut consequerentur, qui passim per omnia Thraciae castella, fessi morbis ac longitudine viae, relictis erant. Receptis omnibus ingressi rursus iter per Chersonesum Hellespontum perveniunt / In the meantime, the consul, who passed through the regions of Aenos and Maroneia, received information about the defeat of the royal fleet at Myonessus and the evacuation of Lysimachia. The latter caused him greater satisfaction than the first, more of all things, which happened on their arrival there, just as they found the city full of supplies of every kind, like being prepared for the arrival of the army, because they expected to be in dire need and difficulties in the siege of the city. For a few days they stayed there, to wait for the arrival of luggage and the sick, who, exhausted from illness and the length of the march were left in all the fortifications of Thrace. When everything was ready, they resumed their march through Chersonese and arrived at the Hellespont“ (Liv. 37.33.1-4).

It makes an impression that the Romans passed within reach Aenos and Maroneia; in these cities there where, according to another report of Livy, garrisons of Antiochus III (Liv. 37.60.7).

Appian presented some more details on the establishment of Roman control over the Thracian Chersonese:

„οὕτω δ' αὐτῆς ὁ Ἀντίοχος αἰσθόμενος Χερρόνησόν τε καὶ Λυσιμάχειαν ἐπιμελῶς ὠχύρου, μέγα, ὥσπερ ἦν, τὸ ἔργον ἠγούμενος ἐπὶ Ῥωμαίοις, ὅπου γε καὶ τὴν ἄλλην Θράκην διελθεῖν στρατοπέδῳ δυσόδευτον αὐτοῖς ἂν ἐγένετο καὶ δύσβατον, εἰ μὴ Φίλιππος διέφερεν. ἀλλ' ὁ Ἀντίοχος ὢν καὶ τὰ ἄλλα κουφόνους ἀεὶ καὶ ταχὺς ἐς μεταβολήν, ἐπεὶ τῆς ἥσσης ἐπύθετο τῆς περὶ Μυόννησον, πάμπαν ἐξεπλάγη, νομίσας αὐτῷ τὸ δαιμόνιον ἐπιβουλεύειν: παρὰ γὰρ λόγον ἕκαστα χωρεῖν, Ῥωμαίων μὲν ἐν τῇ θαλάσῃ κρατούντων, ἐν ἧῖ πολὺ προύχειν αὐτὸς ἐνόμιζε, Ῥοδίων δ' Ἀννίβαν ἐς Παμφυλίαν κατακεκλεικότων, Φιλίππου δὲ Ῥωμαίους παραπέμποντος ἀβάτους ὁδοῦς, ὃν μάλιστα μνησικακήσειν αὐτοῖς ὢν ἔπαθεν ὑπελάμβανεν. ὑπὸ δὴ τῶνδε πάντων ἐκταρασσόμενός τε, καὶ θεοῦ βλάπτοντος ἤδη τοὺς λογισμούς, ὅπερ ἅπασι προσιόντων ἀτυχημάτων ἐπιγίγνεται, Χερρόνησον ἐξέλιπεν ἀλογίστως, πρὶν καὶ ἐς ὄψιν ἐλθεῖν τοῖς πολεμίοις, οὔτε μετενεγκῶν ὅσος ἦν ἐν αὐτῇ σῖτος σεσωρευμένος πολὺς ἢ ὄπλα ἢ χρήματα ἢ μηχαναί, οὔτε ἐμπρήσας, ἀλλ' ὑγιεῖς ἀφορμὰς τοσάσδε τοῖς πολεμίοις καταλιπών. Λυσιμαχέας τε αὐτῷ καθάπερ ἐκ πολιορκίας συμφεύγοντας μετ' οἰμωγῆς, ἅμα γυναιξὶ καὶ παιδίοις, ὑπερέωρα, μόνου τοῦ διάπλου τοῦ περὶ Ἄβυδον εἶρξαι τοὺς πολεμίους ἐπινοῶν, καὶ τὴν λοιπὴν ἔτι ἐλπίδα τοῦ πολέμου πᾶσαν ἐν τούτῳ τιθέμενος. οὐ μὴν οὔτε τὸν διάπλου ἐφύλαξεν ὑπὸ θεοβλαβείας, ἀλλ' ἐς τὸ μεσόγειον ἠπείχθη ἐπανελθεῖν, φθάνων τοὺς πολεμίους, οὐδέ τινα φυλακὴν ἐν τῷ διάπλῳ κατέλιπεν. οἱ δὲ Σκιπίωνες ἐπεὶ τῆς ἀναχωρήσεως αὐτοῦ ἐπύθοντο, Λυσιμάχειάν τε δρόμῳ κατέλαβον, καὶ τῶν ἐν Χερρονήσῳ θησαυρῶν τε καὶ ὄπλων κρατήσαντες τὸν Ἑλλήσποντον ἔρημον ὄντα φυλακῆς εὐθὺς [...] / Before Antiochus to hear of that [the outcome of the Battle of Myonessus] he was fortifying Chersonese and Lysimachia with the greatest attention, thinking, as it was really, that this was very important for defense against the Romans, who would have difficulty passing through the rest of Thrace, if Philip had not guided them. But Antiochus, who was generally frivolous and unstable, when he heard about the defeat at Myonessus, he was completely panicked and thought that the fate turned its back on him. Everything had turned against his expectations. The Romans defeated him by sea, where he thought he had great superiority; the Rhodians blocked Hannibal in Pamphylia; Philip helped the Romans to pass through impassable roads, while Antiochus assumed, that he [Philip V] would not forget what he suffered from them. Everything made him nervous, and the deity began to destroy his thinking abilities, as it always happens, when misfortunes multiply. So, he abandoned Chersonese for no reason, even before the enemy appeared, without even taking care of burning the large supplies, which he gathered there, i.e.: grain, weapons, money, machines; left all these military resources in good condition for the enemy. He paid no attention to the Lysimachians, who, as after a siege, accompanied him

with complaints on his escape, together with their wives and children. He intended only to prevent the enemy from passing at Abydos and he rested his hope of success entirely on this. He was so wrapped up that he didn't even protect the passage, but hurried to the interior of his kingdom, to pre-empt the enemy, without even leaving guards on the Straits. When the Scipio brothers learned of his retreat, they quickly captured Lysimachia with the first attack, seized the treasure and weapons in Chersonese, passed the unguarded Hellespont“ (App., Syr., 6.28-29).

Although quite circumstantial, this narrative is important for defining the chronological order of the events. The text itself categorically rejects some misunderstandings in historiography, more specifically the allegation for abandonment of Chersonese only after the Battle of Magnesia (maintained by ЦБЕТКОБА 2008: 232) and the capture of Lysimachia after the crossing to Asia Minor (declared by ΠΕΤΚΟΒ 2011: 44). It's become clear that by the autumn of 190 BC, when the decisive naval battle of Myonessus is dated, Antiochus III made efforts to keep his possessions in Thrace. Upon learning of the result, however, he withdrew his forces from Chersonese (RICH 2015: 94-95).

A fragment of Diodorus of Sicily provides another look to the same events:

„Ὅτι ὁ Ἀντίοχος διὰ τὴν ἦτταν ταπεινωθεὶς ἔκρινε τῆς μὲν Εὐρώπης ἐξίστασθαι, περὶ δὲ τῆς Ἀσίας διαγωνίζεσθαι. Καὶ προσέταξε τοῖς Λυσιμαχεῦσι πανδημεὶ τὴν πόλιν ἐκλιπεῖν, εἰς δὲ τὰς κατὰ τὴν Ἀσίαν πόλεις μετοικῆσαι. Καὶ ἔδοξε πᾶσιν ἀφρόνως βεβουλεῦσθαι καὶ πόλιν ἐπικαιρότατα κειμένην πρὸς τὸ διακωλύσαι τοὺς πολεμίους ἐκ τῆς Εὐρώπης εἰς τὴν Ἀσίαν περαιοῦν τὰς δυνάμεις ἀκονιτὶ προέσθαι τοῖς πολεμίοις. Ἀκολουθῶς δὲ τῇ διαλήψει ταύτῃ καὶ τὸ τῶν ἀποτελεσμάτων ἔργον ἐπληρώθη. Ὁ γὰρ Σκιπίων τὴν πόλιν καταλαβὼν ἔρημον αὐτομάτως εὐημέρησε ταύτην παραλαβὼν / Being resigned to the defeat, Antiochus decided to leave Europe and to concentrate on the defense of Asia. He ordered the inhabitants of Lysimachia to abandon their city and to find refuge in the cities of Asia. The general opinion was that this decision was stupid, and he left without a fight, in the hands of the enemy, a city, most conveniently located for preventing movement of enemy forces from Europe to Asia. The subsequent course of events fully confirmed that assessment, because Scipio, finding the city abandoned, achieved great success by seizing it“ (Diod., 29.5.1).

The text explicitly claims that the inhabitants of Lysimachia were evacuated to Asia by order of the Syrian monarch. This contradicts somewhat the above-quoted passage of Appian, after which at least some of the inhabitants of the city resisted the Romans. The simplest and most logical explanation is

that Antiochus III withdrew his forces, but some of the Lysimachians decided to voluntarily stay in the city and protect it. However, they were defeated by the first attack and the city was quickly captured.

Conclusions

On the basis of the whole overview, proposed in this work, some significant observations regarding the first passage of Roman troops through the Thracian lands can be noticed.

First of all, the ancient references as a whole don't contain enough details – especially spatial and chronological landmarks – on the passage through Thrace. The authorship of the idea of the unusual march is also controversial: Livy attributes it to Lucius Cornelius Scipio, but Appian – to his brother, Publius Cornelius Scipio Africanus. It is possible to assume only the general direction of movement of the Roman forces, which most of the way probably followed the route of the future Via Egnatia.

The present paper clearly shows that the diligent assistance of the Macedonian king can be convincingly explained by some conquests of Antiochus III in Thrace. They once belonged to Philip V, as it is indicated by Cassius Dio. This provides a convincing explanation of the comprehensive support that Philip V of Macedon gave to the Romans in the Syrian war (192 – 188 BC).

The chronology of the Thracian march causes some difficulties. In the scientific literature is already paid attention to the unusually long transition through the Thracian lands. Its duration is implicitly deduced from the available information of the ancient works; it seems that the passage of the whole distance of about 400 km, between the eastern borders of Macedonia near Abdera to Lysimachia, must have taken the Romans four or five months (GRAINGER 2002: 308). Any convincing explanation of this extremely slow movement has not been found. There is a suggestion for resistance of Thracian and Seleucid forces in the country, or a need to ensure road safety through construction of fortifications (GRAINGER 2002: 310). None of these suggestions can find support in the available sources: there is evidence of only very limited and insignificant military actions between the Macedonian borders and the Thracian Chersonese, while the provision for the construction works on the road facilities is attributed entirely to Philip V of Macedon.

All the evidences demonstrate a remarkable authority of Philip V among the Thracians. However, his authority was not unlimited, insofar as the need to maintain peace with them is explicitly stated in one of the sources. Another reference mentioned that he scattered some „hostile Thracians“ (τοὺς ἐπικειμένους Θρᾷκας διακόπτων). The latter situation was presupposed by a

desire to guarantee the safety of the Roman troops. There is also information about two battles of the Roman army: an allied unit got into a fight with the Thracians, as the place is not explicitly stated; military actions were also carried out in capturing Lysimachia.

The information about the Thracian fortifications (Thraciae castella), mentioned by Livy, is puzzling. Due to insufficient knowledge, no unambiguous interpretation can be offered; they seem to have been controlled by the Romans and possibly by the Macedonian king.

The examined campaign is involved by modern researchers in interpreting another information on the history of the same area. At that time is sought the signing of a treaty of alliance between Rome and the Sapaean; it is mentioned in the sources of later events, but it's unknown when was signed (ПЕТКОВ 2011: 70). The presence of the Scipios in Southern Thrace may also explain the name of a Thracian tribe, preserved as Corneli(i) in the manuscripts of Livy. They were among the four tribes that attacked Vulso in 188 BC; it is interesting that the tribe bear the gentile name of the two brothers, leading the Roman army in 190 BC (ИЛИЕВ 2015: 212). Direct grounds for supporting these two assumptions are not found in the presented ancient texts, but there are no grounds for their rejection too.

Undoubtedly, the Roman army successfully passed through the Thracian lands since no significant losses were reported. However, as the above quoted ancient texts clearly show, the Romans had to fight in Thrace, although on a limited scale.

Bibliography

ДЕЛЕВ 2017: Делев, Петър. „Древна Тракия в края на III и през първата половина на II в. пр. Хр.“. В: Сборник в чест на XX години програми по египтология в Нов български университет. София: Изток-Запад, 2017.

ИЛИЕВ 2022: Илиев, Йордан. „Тракийският поход на Сципионите през 190 г. пр. Хр.“ // Годишна научна конференция: 110 години традиция, качество, престиж. София, 12-13 април 2022 г. Част II. София: Военна академия „Г. С. Раковски“, 2022, 282-289.

ИЛИЕВ 2023: Илиев, Йордан. Тракия и траките в политиката на Рим и Македония по времето на Филип V (221 – 179 г. пр. Хр.). Плевен: izdavam.com, 2023.

ПЕТКОВ 2011: Петков, Пламен. Военно-политически отношения на тракийските владетели в Европейския Югоизток между 230/229 г. пр. Хр. – 45/46 г. сл. Хр. В. Търново: Фабер, 2011.

ТАЧЕВА 1997: Тачева, Маргарита. История на българските земи в древността през елинистическата и римската епоха. София: Унив. изд. „Св. Климент Охридски“, 1997.

ЦВЕТКОВА 2008: Цветкова, Юлия. История на Тракийския Херсонес (от Троянската война до времето на римското завоевание). В. Търново: Фабер, 2008.

DMITRIEV 2018: Dmitriev, Sviatoslav. „Roman-Syrian War (192 – 188 BCE)“. In: The Encyclopedia of Diplomacy. John Weley & Sons, 2018, 1-6.

ERDKAMP 2017: Erdkamp, Paul. „The War against Antiochus III, 191 – 188 BC“. In: The Encyclopedia of Ancient Battles. John Wiley & Sons, 2017, 1-9.

GRAINGER 2002: Grainger, John D. The Roman War of Antiochos the Great. Leiden & Boston: Brill, 2002.

GRAINGER 2015: Grainger, John D. The Seleukid Empire of Antiochus III (223 – 187 BC). Barnsley: Pen & Sword Books Ltd., 2015.

HAMMOND & WALBANK 2001: Hammond, N.G.L., Frank W. Walbank. A History of Macedonia, volume III: 336 – 167 BC. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001.

ILIEV 2015: Iliev, Jordan. „Gn. Manlius Vulso’s March through Thrace in 188 BC according to Livy’s manuscript tradition“. In: Paola Schirripa (ed.). Greci e Romani sulle sponde del Mar Nero. Aristonothos – Scritti per il Mediterraneo antico, 15. Milano: Ledizioni, 2019, 209-228.

RICH 2015: Rich, John. „Appian, Polybius and the Romans’ war with Antiochus the Great: a study in Appian’s sources and methods“. In: K. Welch (ed.). Appian’s Roman History: Empire and Civil War. Swansea: Classical Press of Wales, 2015.

WALBANK 2014: Walbank, Frank W. Philip V of Macedon. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2014.